
**Using pedagogical approaches through fairytales for pre-schoolers in English
as second language**

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Abstract. Practice shows that fairy tales are a source of early learning a foreign language. As an element of folklore, fairy tales have great potential for the development of moral qualities, mental abilities and volitional behavior. They vividly express the identity of the people, its culture, traditions, moral foundations, features of national life.

Key words: preschool age, fairy tale, folklore, moral principles, national way of life, self-expression, education, upbringing.

INTRODUCTION

The author of fairy tales impeccably tells young listeners about the difficulty of choosing an honest path, the bitterness of loneliness and the joy of friendship, the illusions of fear that divide people in different countries, sincerity and trust, the basis of peace and happiness on earth. In fairy tales, children encounter complex events and emotions such as life and death, love and hate, betrayal and lies. These events are described in a special, marvelous way that is accessible to the child's

understanding.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

We will reflect on the possibilities of the fairy tale as a meaningful basis for language learning and how it contributes to the solution of educational tasks. Developmental direction is of paramount importance in the initial stage of learning, as the foundations of many essential skills are laid and their initial development takes place in the first year of schooling. A fairy tale is an excellent material for solving developmental tasks. One of the most important goals of the developmental aspect is the formation of motivational needs. It is in the initial period that the teacher must create a stable motivation to learn a foreign language. A fairy tale, which is always interesting to children with its content basis, contributes greatly to the creation of motivation to learn a foreign language. A fairy tale in a foreign language allows the child to enter the marvelous plot of a fairy tale created by representatives of other nations, to get acquainted with folk heroes of the country where the fairy tale was born. The introduction of exercises based on fairy tales into the lesson plan will immediately attract children's attention. A fairy tale in a foreign language helps the teacher to turn a compulsory learning process into an exciting, desirable and expected process for the child. It helps the teacher to attract children to study, to make them voluntary to seek knowledge, to form a positive attitude to the educational process.

An important goal of the developmental aspect is the formation of communication skills. In children of senior preschool age, personal, role, business competence is formed. A fairy tale in a foreign language always causes children's need for

communication, because its content corresponds to the interests of children and the needs of their age [1].

Special attention was paid to the aspect of linguocultural knowledge of a foreign language in preschool children. A child is a rich source of easy access to this information - a source reflecting the cultural heritage of a particular country, a fairy tale. This resource provides an opportunity to study the elements of national culture expressed in the standard of literary language. Linguistic and cultural aspects are always vividly expressed in fairy tales, which are a separate component of educational content and form the ability to communicate in a foreign language, providing additional knowledge.

When using fairy tales as a content basis for teaching in MTT, children's interest in the culture of a foreign language is formed and realized through the study of: the culture of the country in this language (history, geographical information). about the life of peers, everyday life, customs, interests, music, painting, clothes, holidays, hobbies); about the relevant elements of world culture; about the relationship between the culture of a foreign language and native language (on all the above components).

A fairy tale, being the content basis of teaching, is effectively used to solve educational tasks. Teaching conversational speech on the basis of a fairy tale forms children's ideas about a foreign language as a means of interpersonal communication in all its forms, equal to the native language. In terms of content, a fairy tale is an excellent means of organizing the process of mastering various skills of communication in a foreign language. The process of formation of speech

skills when using a fairy tale as a content basis of training is aimed at the development of communicative training, the formation of skills to use a foreign language as a means of communication. The story, which is the content basis of teaching speaking, helps students to get involved in the process of communication and co-creation. On the basis of the content of the story it is possible to create various role situations. It is known that the first acquaintance with English grammar often causes frustration and boredom in children. The child, forced to internalize vocabulary, phonetic material and speech skills, often loses motivation for further language learning, repetition of grammatical material, practicing grammatical skills - the most difficult thing for a child of 5-7 years - to listen to the dry remarks of the teacher. . There is only one way out of this situation - to turn the agenda into a game. L.S. According to Vygotsky, "the game - a natural form of child labor, a holistic form of activity, preparation for future life. A child always plays, but his game is very logical, it fully corresponds to his age and interests and includes elements leading to the development of necessary skills and competencies" [3] [3].

"Be like children!" defines the teacher's behavior in the classroom [4]. Using fairy tales in lessons, children begin to compose their own fairy tales. Therefore, it is necessary to strictly adhere to the principle of creativity, freedom, which implies three rules no:

1. Do not limit the content and ways of presenting the fairy tale.
2. Do not give any explanation to the tale.
3. Do not interrupt the child's story unnecessarily.

One of the most important conditions for teaching schoolchildren a foreign language is the formation of their interest in learning a foreign language. Therefore, the lesson should be used in an activity where children do not feel tired and work with enthusiasm.

One of the main factors of early learning a foreign language is the wide provision of the game basis of learning, the use of the game as the main source of motivation in solving learning problems. Therefore, experts in foreign languages consider the game as one of the most effective tools of the cognitive process of the child. Lexical games help to better understand the meaning of words included in the vocabulary, to consolidate and activate them. In the process of play, children's vocabulary increases, they learn to associate newly introduced words with the learned words and use them in speech [3].

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

Characters of fairy tales are given a certain character, they act in certain circumstances. The absence of redundant information allows semanticizing the linguistic material in the same way as a visual image. This is one of the advantages of a fairy tale over a complex literary work. Psychologists have found that cartoons emphasizing various characteristics of an object are recognized much faster than photographs of the object. The reason for this is that photographs have too much detail and unnecessary information.

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